

Research Proposal: Adaptive Learning in Imperfect Information Games – A Case Study in Heads-Up Poker

Objective

The objective of this research is to investigate how an adaptive system, such as an amateur poker player or an AI model, can outperform a professional poker player in heads-up scenarios without external assistance. By leveraging reinforcement learning, opponent modeling, and behavioral analysis, this study aims to:

1. Develop scalable learning frameworks for environments with incomplete information.
2. Contribute to advancements in AI techniques for decision-making under uncertainty, adversarial environments, and strategic planning.

This research will benchmark frameworks with potential real-world applications, including healthcare diagnostics, autonomous systems, and financial risk management.

Practical Objective

The goal is to design an AI model that mimics the learning trajectory of an amateur player, beginning with limited knowledge and evolving through iterative observation and adaptation. The study will explore the conditions and likelihood under which such a model can consistently outperform professional AI or human players. Key factors to be analyzed include cognitive, strategic, and algorithmic components necessary for success.

Current Findings and Novelty of this Research

While there has been substantial work on AI systems in poker, such as Libratus and Pluribus, which have successfully defeated professional players, these models heavily relied on external computational power and resources during training. Existing studies focus on AI performance using extensive pre-training or self-play, leveraging significant external assistance to develop near-perfect strategies.

Your research stands out by shifting the focus to:

1. **Learning Through Interaction:** Investigating skill acquisition and strategy development purely through iterative gameplay, without external computational aid.
2. **Heads-Up Play Dynamics:** Concentrating on real-time adaptation in heads-up scenarios where the amateur learns exclusively by observing and exploiting patterns in professional play.
3. **Innate Human Traits:** Emphasizing the role of inherent abilities like IQ, memory, and adaptability in enabling an amateur to outperform a professional, thus exploring human competitive potential alongside AI simulations.

This perspective bridges a critical gap in the field by prioritizing the innate qualities and learning processes required for success, rather than relying on pre-defined or externally enhanced AI strategies.

Research Blueprint

Methodology

1. Simulation Environment:

- Develop a poker simulation platform for heads-up matches between a pre-trained "professional" AI and an adaptive "amateur" AI.

2. AI Frameworks:

- **Professional AI:** Trained using advanced algorithms such as Monte Carlo Tree Search (MCTS) and Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) to simulate expert-level play.
- **Amateur AI:** Initialized with minimal domain knowledge and trained iteratively using reinforcement learning techniques like Q-learning and Actor-Critic methods.

3. Adaptation Analysis:

- Measure learning rate, behavioral patterns, and decision-making improvements.
- Monitor strategies evolving in response to professional playstyles, focusing on adaptability and innovation.

4. Performance Metrics:

- Winning percentage across iterations.
- Strategy convergence, emphasizing the ability to exploit professional weaknesses.
- Efficiency of decision-making under various conditions.

5. Real-World Relevance:

- Validate the AI frameworks against problems like risk modeling, negotiation, and opponent behavior prediction in competitive settings.

Tools Required

1. Programming Frameworks:

- Python with libraries like PyTorch or TensorFlow for AI training.
- Poker simulation tools such as OpenAI Gym or custom-built platforms.

2. Algorithmic Models:

- Deep Q-Networks (DQN), Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO), and Imitation Learning to observe and replicate expert behavior.

3. Evaluation Platforms:

- Statistical analysis tools like R or Python's SciPy for performance metrics.
- Cloud infrastructure (e.g., AWS, Google Cloud) for large-scale simulations.

4. Behavior Analysis:

- Visualization tools like TensorBoard to track and interpret AI decision-making.
 - Frameworks for reinforcement learning tracking and analysis.
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Research Scope

This research will focus on:

- Developing adaptive learning strategies tailored to imperfect information environments.
- Creating scalable models that generalize beyond poker to domains requiring strategic and uncertain decision-making.
- Analyzing game-theoretic principles to enhance AI's ability to predict, counter, and exploit opponents' strategies.

The inclusion of poker as a testing environment is intentional due to its balance of strategy, chance, and adaptability, offering a robust platform for validating AI capabilities.

Practical Contributions

1. Transferable AI Solutions:

- Develop adaptive learning frameworks applicable to domains like healthcare diagnostics, resource allocation, and autonomous systems.

2. Behavioral Insights:

- Advance opponent modeling and strategy formulation in competitive environments, leveraging concepts from game theory and real-world adversarial scenarios.

3. Framework for Imperfect Information:

- Contribute to research in scalable AI systems for negotiation, resource allocation, and human-AI collaboration, with practical implications for industries relying on decision-making under uncertainty.
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Poker Example and Personal Motivation

As an undergraduate in Computer Science with a passion for game theory, competition, and AI applications in games, my interest in heads-up poker stems from its unique combination of strategy, uncertainty, and adaptability. The research aligns with my fascination for how AI can learn and thrive in imperfect information environments, drawing parallels between poker strategies and broader AI challenges like adversarial learning and decision-making under pressure. My previous exploration of poker's strategic nuances has informed the choice of this domain, emphasizing the intersection of academic inquiry and personal interest.

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